

1 **Title Page**

2 Journal: Trees - Structure and Function

3 Title: Digging deeper - Soil water availability reshapes fine root distribution in hybrid poplar
4 (*Populus nigra* × *P. maximowiczii*) short-rotation coppice plantation

5 Authors:

6 Berhongaray, Gonzalo ^{1, 2 *}

7 Tripathi, Abhishek ^{3,4,5}

8 Fischer, Milan ^{3,4}

9 Orság, Matěj ^{3,4}

10 Trnka, Miroslav ^{3,4}

11 John King ⁶

12

13 ¹ ICiAgro Litoral (UNL-CONICET). Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias – Universidad Nacional del Litoral,
14 Kreder 2805 – Esperanza, CP 3080, Argentina. bgonzalo@agro.uba.ar ORCID: 0000-0002-3662-
15 8583 . *corresponding author

16 ² Department of Biology, Centre of Excellence on Plants and Ecosystems (PLECO), University of
17 Antwerp, B-2610 Wilrijk, Belgium

18 ³ Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4b, 603 00
19 Brno, Czech Republic

20 ⁴ Mendel University in Brno, Institute of Agrosystems and Bioclimatology, Zemědělská 1, 613
21 00 Brno, Czech Republic

22 ⁵ Macrocosmos Creations Private Limited, Bangalore, KA560085, India

23 ⁶ Department of Forestry and Environmental Resources, North Carolina State University,
24 Raleigh, NC 27695, USA

25 **Acknowledgements**

26 We acknowledge the support of the PLECO Research Center of Excellence and of Prof. Reinhart
27 Ceulemans who also provided useful criticisms on an earlier version of the manuscript.

1 **Abstract**

2 Fine roots play a critical role in water and nutrient uptake, contributing significantly to the
3 ecosystem carbon cycle. This study investigates the effects of soil water availability on the
4 vertical distribution of fine root annual production and turnover rates in hybrid poplar (*Populus*
5 *nigra* × *P. maximowiczii*, clone J-105) short-rotation coppice plantation. We hypothesized that
6 reduced throughfall would lead to a deeper vertical distribution of fine roots and affect their
7 annual production and turnover rates. The study was conducted in a drought experiment
8 established in a coppiced poplar plantation in the Czech Republic. Root biomass and in-growth
9 cores were used to quantify root vertical distribution, production, and turnover rates under
10 control and drought (throughfall reduction) treatments. Root distributions were modeled using
11 the asymptotic equation and the logistic dose-response curve. Although total fine root biomass
12 (255 g DM m⁻²; 0-60 cm) and production (298 g DM m⁻² y⁻¹; 0-60 cm) were not significantly
13 affected by drought, the vertical distribution of fine roots was influenced by soil water
14 availability. Model results show that at lower soil water content in May (20%) corresponded to
15 a greater proportion of roots (50% roots) at deeper soil layers as compared with higher soil water
16 content (35%), where only 20% of roots were allocated to deeper layers. Our findings highlight
17 the importance of accounting for the plasticity in root distributions when modeling drought
18 impacts on ecosystem processes. Shifts in the vertical distribution of fine roots can profoundly
19 impact soil carbon inputs and nutrient uptake efficiencies, which are not fully captured by
20 changes in total root biomass alone. Ecosystem models should incorporate root distribution
21 dynamics to improve predictions of terrestrial carbon cycling under drought conditions.

22

23 **Keywords:** Drought, Biomass, Fine root biomass, Turnover rate, Vertical distribution.

24

25 **Key message:** Soil moisture shapes the vertical distribution of fine roots in poplar, highlighting
26 root plasticity as a key trait for modeling ecosystem responses to changing water availability.

1 Introduction

2 The search for renewable energy sources has led to an increased interest in short rotation
3 coppice (SRC) plantations of fast-growing trees, such as poplars (*Populus* spp.) among others
4 (Králík et al. 2023; Schweier et al. 2017; Zalesny Jr et al. 2019). The increasing prevalence of
5 drought events due to climate change poses a significant threat to these plantations (Forster et
6 al. 2023), impacting their productivity and carbon sequestration potential. These trees have the
7 potential to be used as a bioenergy source (Aylott et al. 2008) and as a means of sequestering
8 carbon in the soil (Ferré et al. 2021). The belowground biomass (0-60 cm depth), comprising
9 approximately 30% of the overall tree biomass, represents a significant yet often overlooked
10 component (Berhongaray and Ceulemans 2015). This biomass can be divided into two distinct
11 categories: coarse roots with a relatively long lifespan, and fine roots, with a lifespan similar to
12 that of leaves (Guo et al. 2021; Withington et al. 2006). Fine roots are an important component
13 of the ecosystem carbon cycle, and play a critical role in water and nutrient uptake (Block et al.
14 2006a). Fine root productivity often exceeds aboveground productivity in forest ecosystems due
15 to high rates of turnover (Al Afas et al. 2008; An et al. 2017; Berhongaray et al. 2013), making
16 the process of fine root production and turnover a large carbon input to soil (Berhongaray et al.
17 2019; Kengdo et al. 2023). However, fine root turnover rate varies among different plant species
18 (Brunner et al. 2013) and is influenced by environmental factors (Block et al. 2006a; Brunner et
19 al. 2013a; Maeght et al. 2013; McCormack and Guo 2014).

20 Fine roots, characterized by their delicate structure and high turnover rates, serve as the primary
21 interface between plants and the soil environment. They play a pivotal role in water and nutrient
22 uptake, actively absorbing essential resources from the soil solution to support plant growth and
23 development (Bardgett et al. 2014; McCormack et al. 2015). Moreover, fine roots contribute
24 significantly to the carbon cycle through respiration, releasing carbon dioxide into the soil
25 (Abramoff et al. 2024). The continuous turnover of fine roots, involving their growth,
26 senescence, and decomposition, further enhances carbon inputs to the soil, influencing soil
27 organic matter dynamics and microbial activity (Guo et al. 2022). The rhizosphere, the zone of
28 soil directly influenced by fine roots, is a hotspot of microbial interactions, where roots release
29 exudates that attract and support diverse microbial communities (Sasse et al. 2018). These
30 interactions can facilitate nutrient acquisition, enhance plant stress tolerance, and contribute to
31 overall ecosystem functioning (Philippot et al. 2013). However, there is still methodological
32 challenges of quantifying fine root mass and the potential impact of sample treatment (i.e.
33 picking duration) on estimates, particularly for dead roots, which are more fragile and difficult
34 to distinguish from soil organic debris. This can lead to underestimation and higher variability in

1 dead root biomass (McCormack et al., 2015). These issues are further compounded when
2 studying deep roots, where recovery efficiency tends to be lower (Pierret et al., 2016; Schenk &
3 Jackson, 2002).

4 While previous studies have examined root responses to drought in poplar, particularly in young
5 or newly established plantations (Broeckx et al. 2013; Zou et al. 2022), there remains a limited
6 understanding of how drought specifically affects the vertical distribution of fine roots in mature
7 SRC poplar plantations. This knowledge gap is crucial to address, as the vertical distribution of
8 fine roots directly influences resource acquisition strategies and overall plantation resilience
9 under water-limited conditions. Studies on other poplar plantations or tree species have shown
10 that drought can induce shifts in root distribution, often towards deeper soil layers where
11 moisture may be more readily available (Hu et al. 2024; Schenk and Jackson 2002b). However,
12 the extent to which these findings apply to mature SRC poplar plantations remains unclear, as
13 these systems may exhibit unique root dynamics due to their repeated coppicing cycles, high
14 planting densities, and rapid shoot regrowth after harvest (Ceulemans and Deraedt 1999). Such
15 management features can lead to sustained high nutrient and water demand (Deckmyn et al.
16 2004; Herve and Ceulemans 1996; Wildy et al. 2004), potentially altering root turnover rates,
17 depth distribution, and the balance between fine and coarse root biomass compared to non-
18 coppiced stands. Although the impact of drought on root biomass and overall growth in SRC has
19 been investigated (Meyer et al. 2021; Regier et al. 2009), there is a paucity of research
20 specifically examining the effects of drought on the vertical distribution of fine roots in these
21 systems. Understanding how drought alters the spatial configuration of root systems is crucial
22 for predicting the resilience of SRC plantations under water-limited conditions and optimizing
23 their management for sustainable bioenergy production.

24 Accurately representing root dynamics in ecosystem models is crucial for predicting the
25 responses of agroforestry systems to environmental change, particularly drought. However,
26 current models often oversimplify root processes, neglecting the dynamic vertical distribution
27 of fine roots and their crucial role in water and nutrient uptake (Bardgett et al. 2014; McCormack
28 et al. 2015). This oversimplification also extends to the treatment of deep roots, which are
29 increasingly recognized as key contributors to ecosystem services such as groundwater
30 regulation, soil carbon sequestration, and nutrient cycling, yet remain underrepresented in both
31 empirical studies and models due to the challenges of observation (Pierret et al. 2016).
32 Addressing these gaps is essential, as inaccurate representation of root dynamics can lead to
33 flawed predictions of carbon and water cycling, potentially hindering the development of
34 effective management strategies for sustainable production.

1 The objective of the current study is to investigate the effects of drought on the vertical
2 distribution of fine roots in SRC, with a focus on the annual production and turnover rates. We
3 hypothesize that drought will induce a shift in root distribution towards deeper soil layers, as
4 plants seek to access moisture at greater depths. This shift in root distribution may also lead to
5 changes in fine root production and turnover rates, reflecting adaptive strategies to water stress.
6 The findings have important implications for improving the representation of root dynamics in
7 ecosystem models which often consider varying root depth but constant vertical distribution
8 (e.g., Fischer et al. 2018, Schmidt-Walter et al. 2020). Incorporating dynamically changing
9 vertical profiles in response to seasonal variation of soil water availability may enhance the
10 predictive accuracy of agroforestry responses to drought.

11

12 **Materials and methods**

13 *Experimental site and plantation*

14 To investigate fine root depth distribution and dynamics, we took advantage of a well-
15 established SRC polar plantation with established root systems and analyzed responses to
16 recurring droughts. The study was carried out at Domanínek, Czech Republic (49.521°N and
17 16.235°E, at an elevation of 578 m above sea level), a village near Bystřice nad Pernštejnem, and
18 located in the Českomoravská vrchovina upland region. The climate of the region is
19 characterized as cool and wet, with an average annual precipitation of 610 mm (Fig. 1) and a
20 mean annual temperature of 7.5 °C (1981–2010). The soil is a deep Cambisol influenced by gleyic
21 processes with a limited amount of gravels (<10%) in the soil profile. Soil data were obtained
22 from the pedological survey carried out between 2007 and 2012 at the plantation (Table 1).
23 Briefly, the pedological survey involved the opening of four soil pits at specific coordinates. Each
24 soil pit was carefully described, documenting the horizons encountered, their color, structure,
25 and the presence of fragments of rocks, stones, or mineral material. Soil samples were taken at
26 each horizon. In April 2001, a 1.5 ha plantation of the hybrid poplar clone J-105 (*Populus nigra*
27 *L.* × *P. maximowiczii* *H.*) was established using unrooted 25 cm stem cuttings planted in a double
28 row design. The plantation was planted with a tree spacing of 2.5 m between the double-rows
29 and 0.7 m within double-rows, for a theoretical density of 9,216 trees per hectare. The single-
30 stem plantation was harvested at 15–20 cm above the soil surface in winter 2008/2009, which
31 converted it into a multi-stem coppice system. Mechanical weeding in the inter-rows was
32 conducted three times a year using a rototiller. After the establishment phase, weed growth in
33 the inter-rows was managed by mowing, combined with mulching, three times per year. No

1 irrigation, fertilization or herbicide treatments were applied during the experiment. The
2 experimental site and plantation have been previously described in detail (Fischer et al. 2013;
3 Orsag et al. 2018; Tripathi et al. 2018).

4

5

6 **Fig. 1** Seasonal air temperature (above) and cumulative precipitation (below) measured at the
7 Bystřice nad Pernštejnem meteorological station (approximately 1 km from the plantation at the
8 same elevation). The black lines represent the values for the season 2014, while the gray lines
9 represent the values from the previous five years (i.e. 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012 and 2013) and the
10 dotted line the long-term average (1981–2010)

11

12 **(Table 1)**

13

14 *Drought experiment*

15 The drought gradient was established using a throughfall reduction approach, where plastic
16 roofs were installed to intercept 30% of incoming precipitation (See more details in Orsag et al.
17 2018) . This approach aimed to create a range of soil moisture conditions, simulating varying
18 levels of drought stress. However, we acknowledge that soil water movement is a complex

1 process influenced by factors such as soil texture, evapotranspiration rates, and lateral water
 2 flow. In 2011 a throughfall reduction experiment was established in the plantation (Fig. 2). The
 3 experimental design consisted of three blocks and two treatments per block. Each block had two
 4 square plots with a total area of 50 m² (5 x 5 m= 25 m² each treatment plot) representing the
 5 Control and reduced throughfall treatment, hereafter called the Drought treatment (Orsag et al.
 6 2018). Trenches were dug to a depth of 60 cm around each drought plot to prevent horizontal
 7 root growth and lateral water flow. Soil water content was measured using a soil profile probe
 8 (type PR2, Delta-T Devices, Cambridge, UK), monitoring volumetric soil water content (dm³ dm⁻³)
 9 at depths of 10, 20, 30 and 40 cm. The soil volume sampled at each of the four depths was
 10 ~1.5 dm³, and the average of three readings was always taken with the profile probe rotated
 11 120° in the access tube for each measurement point. Three soil water tubes were installed
 12 diagonally across each plot covering inter rows and double-rows positions (3 positions × 2
 13 treatments × 3 blocks = 18 soil water probes in total). The soil water measurements were taken
 14 regularly (once per month) throughout the growing seasons of 2013 and 2014. This allowed us
 15 to track changes in soil moisture in response to the throughfall reduction treatment and assess
 16 the effectiveness of the drought gradient. At the time of this study (2013 – 2014, see below),
 17 the tree density was reduced to 8,700 trees per hectare in the control plots and to 7,300 trees
 18 per hectare in the drought treatment, yielding 3.68 shoots m⁻² and 2.37 shoot m⁻², respectively.
 19

20
 21 **Fig. 2** Schematic representation of the experimental design: a) distribution of blocks (A, B and C)
 22 and treatments (Drought and Control) in the field plot; b) distribution of treatments, in-growth
 23 cores (black dots) and soil water probes (stars) in each block; and c) cross-sectional view of the
 24 roof treatment with in-growth cores, soil water probes and trench. The Drought treatment
 25 (reduced precipitation throughfall) used plastic roof sheets (shelter) to exclude roots and lateral

1 soil water flow. In each treatment, six cores (black dots in Fig. 2b) were taken for root biomass
2 determination and installation of in-growth cores

3

4 *Root biomass and in-growth cores*

5 After three years of Drought treatment root responses were quantified in 2014, consisting of
6 vertical distribution of root biomass, and root production and turnover using the root in-growth
7 core technique (Brunner et al. 2013). The ingrowth core method provides a standardized
8 measure of new root production under controlled soil conditions but may underestimate
9 production due to the absence of existing root networks and may alter root growth patterns
10 compared to undisturbed soil (Brunner et al. 2013). However, in this study the main objective
11 was to compare differences between treatments, and both treatments were assessed using the
12 same method under the same conditions. In February 2014, root biomass distribution was
13 assessed from soil samples collected at 6 locations in each plot (6 locations × 3 blocks × 2
14 treatments = 36 samples) at four sampling depths (0–15 cm, 15–30 cm, 30–45 cm, 45–60 cm)
15 using an 8 cm diameter × 15 cm deep hand-driven corer (Eijkelkamp Agrisearch equipment, The
16 Netherlands). A total of 144 soil samples were collected and immediately processed in the lab
17 (see below) and the root-free soil was kept aside and stored in plastic bags for the installation
18 of in-growth cores. For the in-growth cores, 2.2-mm mesh bags (10 cm diameter × 0.60 m depth)
19 were installed in the sampling holes from the root biomass assessment (n= 36). Each mesh bag
20 was filled with the root-free original soil obtained from the site and care was taken to replicate
21 the original soil horizons and bulk density. To achieve the desired soil bulk density, a manual
22 tamper was used, compacting with more pressure in the lower layers and with less pressure in
23 the upper layers of the soil. Although the pressure used was not measured, measurement of the
24 replaced soil determined that it was similar in bulk density as the surrounding soil. Half of the
25 in-growth cores (n=18), distributed across both treatments, were retrieved after six months and
26 half after ten months, after the peak and end of the growing season, in August (Fischer et al.
27 2013) and November 2014, respectively. Upon retrieval, the in-growth cores were nicely
28 colonized by roots and were divided into four depth increments (0–15 cm, 15–30 cm, 30–45 cm,
29 45–60 cm), yielding a total of 72 samples for each sampling campaign. In-growth core samples
30 were stored in plastic bags in a freezer until processed (Lindström and Stattin 1994).

31 Root biomass and in-growth cores were processed uniformly. Samples were thawed and roots
32 manually picked for 20 min, washed, dried with absorbent paper and weighed. A subset of 10
33 samples were manually picked for 1, 2, 5, 20, 40 and 60 min following an earlier methodological

1 study (Berhongaray *et al.* 2013). Calibration curves were fitted with picking duration study to
2 transform the 20 min biomass into the total biomass at 60 min (for more details see SM1). Roots
3 were sorted into fine (<2 mm) and coarse (>2 mm) classes, washed and put in paper bags for dry
4 mass (DM) determination. Live fine roots were classified into absorptive and transport fine-root
5 pools based on diameter following McCormack *et al.* (2015) and Wang *et al.* (2019). Absorptive
6 roots (0–1 mm, first-order roots) are non-woody, often mycorrhizal tips specialized in water and
7 nutrient uptake, whereas transport roots (1–2 mm, higher-order roots) are thicker, less
8 mycorrhizal, and primarily involved in water and nutrient transport and mechanical support.
9 Dead poplar roots (D; necromass), which were observed only in the 0–1 mm diameter class,
10 were sorted from live roots based on the dark color and the lack of cohesion of the periderm
11 (Jasens *et al.* 1999). Sorted roots were dried at 65 °C to constant mass. Although data from the
12 coarse roots (>2 mm) are also presented, the spatial variation was high, and therefore drawing
13 of inferences from such core sampling should be limited (Levillain *et al.* 2011). Fine root data,
14 however, provided robust insights into root responses to drought.

15 *Fine root production and root turnover*

16 The in-growth core method was the primary method used to measure root biomass production,
17 combined with the decision matrix method (Fairley and Alexander 1985). The decision matrix
18 calculates productivity, mortality and disappearance of fine roots between consecutive sampling
19 dates using data of fine root biomass and necromass. Although this method has been used in
20 sequential coring (Berhongaray *et al.* 2013), we applied it to the in-growth core method,
21 accounting not only for the measured biomass and necromass, but also including the changes in
22 measured biomass and necromass across sampling dates to estimate the root production. Our
23 focus was primarily on fine root production quantified during the growing season, however, it is
24 important to note that our investigation did not encompass the winter months, a period during
25 which significant root mortality typically occurs (Brunner *et al.* 2013b). As such, our analysis did
26 not incorporate calculations related to root mortality. Root production was estimated from the
27 quantity of total root biomass produced (live biomass and necromass) from February to August,
28 and from August to November 2014. Root production is expressed on an annual basis,
29 considering the majority of production occurred from February to November. This assumption
30 is supported by previous studies in temperate *Populus* plantations showing negligible fine root
31 production during winter months (Block *et al.* 2006b), and by local soil temperature records (<
32 5 °C at 0–10 cm) that limit root growth (Pregitzer *et al.* 2000). For more details, see
33 Supplementary Materials (SM2).

1 Fine root turnover rate is defined as the rate at which the roots are being renewed every year
2 (Berhongaray *et al.* 2013). We calculated fine root turnover rate for each diameter class (L1 and
3 L2) as the quotient between root production (g DM m⁻² y⁻¹) and mean root biomass (g DM m⁻²).

4 *Statistical analysis*

5 An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test for differences in fine root biomass, production
6 and turnover between treatments (Control vs. Drought) at each root class/category (D, 0–1 mm,
7 1–2 mm, >2 mm) and soil sampling depth (0–15, 15–30, 30–45 and 45–60 cm). Treatment was
8 considered as the main factor in the ANOVA. Differences were considered significant at P≤0.05.
9 Assumptions on distributions of residuals of the linear models were checked by visual inspection
10 of quantile-quantile probability plots and by analysis of skewness and kurtosis.

11 To analyze the relationship between root depth distributions and drought, the vertical root
12 profile and its relationship with Drought and Control treatments was modeled. Two classic root
13 fitting models widely used for root distributions described and characterized the vertical
14 distribution of the roots. The first one is based on the asymptotic equation (Gale and Grigal
15 1987; Jackson *et al.* 1996)

$$16 \quad Y = 1 - \beta^D, \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

17 where Y is the cumulative root fraction (a proportion between 0 and 1) from the soil surface to
18 depth D (cm), and β is a fitted "extinction coefficient". β is the only parameter estimated in the
19 model and provides a simple numerical index of rooting distribution.

20 The second model is the logistic dose–response curve model (Schenk and Jackson 2002a) given
21 as

$$22 \quad Y = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{D}{D_{50}}\right)^{-c}}, \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

23 where c is the shape parameter (dimensionless), and D₅₀ (cm) is the depth above which 50% of
24 the roots are located. The logistic model (Schenk & Jackson, 2002a) can yield a range of curve
25 shapes depending on parameters c and D₅₀, with c controlling the steepness and D₅₀ indicating
26 the depth above which 50 % of the roots are located. This functional flexibility is particularly
27 relevant given that root depth distributions are highly plastic and context-dependent, shaped
28 by environmental conditions and species-specific traits (Pierret *et al.* 2016). The models were
29 fitted to the cumulative root fraction using evolutionary global optimization via the differential
30 evolution algorithm (Ardia *et al.* 2011; Mullen *et al.* 2011). β , D₅₀ and c parameters were
31 compared for the Drought and Control treatments using ANOVA. Differences were considered

1 significant at $P \leq 0.05$. A Pearson correlation analysis was used to relate root biomass from
2 February 2014 with soil water content at each soil depth in 2013, and root production in 2014
3 with soil water content in 2014. The relationship between soil water content at various time
4 windows and root distribution parameters was also studied. All analyses were performed in R
5 statistical programming software (R CoreTeam 2023).

6

7 **Results**

8 The impact of drought on fine root biomass differed across soil depths and root diameter classes.
9 At the 0–15 cm depth dead fine roots and live fine roots were similar across the treatments
10 (Table 2). As depth increased the differences between the Control and Drought treatments in
11 both dead and live fine roots became more pronounced. For instance, at the 30–45 cm depth,
12 the Control treatment had 7.4 g DM m⁻² of dead fine roots and 22.7 g DM m⁻² of live fine roots,
13 while the Drought treatment had 7.1 g DM m⁻² of dead fine roots and 13.9 g DM m⁻² of live fine
14 roots (Table 2). These results indicate that drought had a negative impact on the fine root
15 biomass of poplars, specifically live fine roots, with the largest impact on the very smallest
16 diameter roots at the 15–45 cm depth range. Regarding to the mass estimation, we remark the
17 need for longer picking durations for dead and absorptive fine roots (SM 1).

18

19 **(Table 2)**

20 There were no statistically significant differences in fine root production at different depths and
21 diameter classes when exposed to Drought treatment compared to the Control (Table 3). Most
22 of the fine root production occurred in the top 30 cm of the soil, with 268 g DM m⁻² y⁻¹ and 230
23 g DM m⁻² y⁻¹ in the Control and Drought treatments, respectively. This accounted for
24 approximately 83% of the total fine root production in the 0–60 cm depth range. Fine root
25 production decreased with increasing depth, with 30.0 g DM m⁻² y⁻¹ and 26.1 g DM m⁻² y⁻¹ in the
26 30–45 cm depth range, and 21.3 g DM m⁻² y⁻¹ and 21.0 g DM m⁻² y⁻¹ in the 45–60 cm depth range,
27 for the control and drought treatments, respectively. The turnover rate of fine roots averaged
28 1.68 y⁻¹ and was not significantly different between the Control and Drought treatment in any
29 depth range. To further elucidate the treatment effects, we calculated response ratios
30 (Drought/Control) for fine root biomass and production at each depth and plotted them against
31 soil moisture levels (Fig. 3).

32

1 (Table 3)

2

3 **Fig. 3** Response Ratios of fine root (0-2 mm) biomass and production to Drought across soil
4 depths. Response ratio = (Drought/Control) - 1. Horizontal bars represent standard errors. No
5 statistically significant differences were found between drought and control at any depth.

6 Parameter β of fine root production was significantly different for the Drought and Control
7 treatments, while β for fine root biomass and the parameters D_{50} and c for fine root biomass
8 and production were not significantly different between the treatments (Table 4). Both models
9 represented well the cumulative distribution of fine roots. The average R^2 of the β parameter
10 yielded 0.99 and ranged from 0.94 to almost unity, while average R^2 of the model with D_{50} and
11 c parameters yielded 0.99 and ranged from 0.95 to almost unity. The mean p-values were 0.0005
12 and 0.0006 for the two models, respectively, and all individual fits were statistically significant
13 with the least significant p-values of 0.006 and 0.005, respectively. This indicates that the vertical
14 distribution was slightly better explained by the two-parameter logistic dose–response curve
15 model as compared to single parameter model We also noted slightly higher R^2 for the fine root
16 production as compared to biomass data vertical distribution fit in the case of both models (R^2
17 of 0.991 vs. 0.988).

18 Vertical distributions of fine root biomass and fine root production were similar. β , D_{50} were
19 correlated with soil water content measured in different months. The months with the highest
20 correlation were April, May, June and August, with May having the highest number of significant
21 correlations with the vertical distribution parameters and the lowest p-value (Fig. 4; see
22 correlation analysis in SM5). High β and z_{50} values (i.e. 0.96 and 15.1) were obtained at low soil
23 water content in May (i.e. 20%), which corresponded to a larger proportion of fine roots at
24 depth, while low β and z_{50} values (i.e. 0.90 and 7.9) were obtained at high soil water content in

1 May (35%), implying a higher proportion of fine roots near the soil surface (Fig. 4 and Fig. 5).
 2 These modeled curves (Fig. 5) were generated by inserting the β and D_{50} values corresponding
 3 to 20% and 35% soil water content (as per the relationships shown in Fig. 4) into the asymptotic
 4 and logistic models, respectively. This approach illustrates how changes in soil moisture
 5 observed in May 2014 between drought and control plots translate into different vertical root
 6 distribution profiles.

7 **(Table 4)**

8

9

10 **Fig. 4** Relationship between the soil water content (%) of the month of May and the β parameter
 11 of the asymptotic equation (left panel; *Jackson et al.* 1996) and the D_{50} parameter of the logistic
 12 dose–response curve model (right panel; *Schenk and Jackson* 2002) fitted to the vertical
 13 distribution of the fine root biomass (FRB; gray circles) and fine root production (FRP; stars)

14

1

2 **Fig. 5** Vertical distribution of root biomass using the asymptotic equation model (left panel;
 3 Jackson *et al.* 1996) and the logistic dose–response curve model (right panel; Schenk and Jackson
 4 2002) at two soil moisture levels (20% and 30% $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$ soil moisture) in May. The horizontal line
 5 represents the 15 cm depth and the values are the cumulative proportion of roots at that depth.
 6 The β parameter and the D_{50} parameter varied according to the relationship with soil moisture
 7 shown in Fig. 4. In the case of the logistic dose–response curve model, an average of c parameter
 8 was used (value of 2.12, *cfr.* Table 4)

9 Discussion

10 Quantification of belowground biomass is currently underrepresented in ecosystem studies of
 11 bioenergy cropping systems under climate extremes such as drought (Brunner *et al.* 2015;
 12 Freitas *et al.* 2021). The results of this study add new data to some of the published results from
 13 poplar plantations in Europe, in particular, the vertical distribution of fine root biomass and fine
 14 root production under different scenarios of soil water availability. Drought stress leads to a
 15 decrease in fine root production in poplar trees (Meyer *et al.* 2021; Regier *et al.* 2009). As young
 16 roots generally are physiologically more active, an increase in root turnover can increase the
 17 water use efficiency, but with an additional carbon cost (Eissenstat *et al.* 2000; Nielsen *et al.*
 18 1994; Vargas *et al.* 2009). Our results show that very fine diameter root biomass can be lower
 19 under drought at specific soil depths, but overall we observed few statistically significant
 20 differences across root diameter classes and soil depths (Table 2). Drought stress on poplar
 21 plantations varies depending on the genotype of the trees and the timing and severity of the
 22 drought stress (Attia *et al.* 2015; Barchet *et al.* 2014). The hybrid used in this study (J-105,
 23 *Populus nigra* \times *P. maximowiczii*) may exhibit particular plasticity in root distribution, potentially

1 enabling adjustments in water uptake strategies under varying soil moisture conditions (Attia et
2 al. 2015). The observed trends in fine root distribution, production, and turnover offer valuable
3 insights into the adaptive strategies of poplar plantations under water stress. The inherent
4 differences in the functional roles and spatial distribution patterns of coarse and fine roots
5 suggest that variations in coarse root distribution may not directly influence the fine root
6 responses observed in this study (McCormack et al. 2015). The primary function of fine roots is
7 resource acquisition, and their distribution is likely more sensitive to localized changes in soil
8 moisture and nutrient availability, whereas coarse roots primarily provide structural support and
9 long-distance transport (Bardgett et al. 2014).

10 *Fine root production and turnover*

11 In this study, we estimated an average fine root productivity of $195 \text{ g DM m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$, which is a high
12 estimate compared to fine root production of $53 \text{ g DM m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ of a newly established SRC
13 plantation in Belgium (Berhongaray et al. 2013). However, our estimates are closer to a longer
14 established poplar plantation in the USA, which estimated an average production of 230 g DM
15 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ (Sprunger et al. 2017). The difference between these sites is likely attributable to
16 differences in the age of the plantations. When young and mature plantations were compared
17 in the same study, fine root productivity was lower in the younger plantation (Block et al. 2006a).
18 Regarding the root methodology used in our study the in-growth method provides reliable
19 estimates for production with much less labor and time compared to methods such as sequential
20 coring or minirhizotrons (Berhongaray et al. 2017; Brunner et al. 2013b). Moreover, as an
21 improvement to the methodology to quantify fine root biomass and picking duration periods
22 proposed earlier (Berhongaray *et al.* 2013), we performed in this study different curves for four
23 categories of roots (SM1) and found that dead roots and absorptive roots (0–1 mm) needed
24 more time to be found, especially the dead roots. Additionally, not only would a longer duration
25 be needed to collect all small fragments of dead roots in a given root sampling (potentially
26 affecting their structural integrity), but it might also necessitate a reduction in the length of
27 observation windows (higher frequency), as a potential adjustment. This has important
28 implications when the objective of the study is the determination of root mortality.

29 Inversely to root production, fine roots die in a process known as root turnover. At a global scale,
30 root turnover is positively correlated with length of the growing season (Gill and Jackson 2000).
31 In hybrid poplars, root production and turnover have been observed to start soon after
32 budbreak and end with leaf fall (Dickmann et al. 2001). Our results on fine root turnover are
33 40% lower than a poplar plantation in Belgium - 2.75 y^{-1} - (Berhongaray et al. 2013). The lower

1 turnover rate of our study might be explained by the 12% (25 days) shorter leaf area duration
2 as compared to the milder Belgian site (Fischer et al. 2018),), which is consistent with the lower
3 mean annual temperature at our site (7.6 °C vs. 10.6 °C) and reflects differences in phenology
4 between continental and maritime climates.. A shorter growing season limits the time window
5 for root production and mortality, potentially reducing annual turnover. These site-specific
6 climatic conditions highlight the importance of considering regional phenology and climate type
7 when comparing turnover rates across sites or when applying these results in ecosystem models.
8 The different turnover rates for absorptive and transport fine roots also confirms previous
9 results where root turnover decreased with increasing root order and diameter (McCormack et
10 al. 2015). Previously, an increase in root turnover in poplar trees has been observed under
11 drought stress (Meyer et al. 2021; Regier et al. 2009). However, there was no effect of the
12 drought treatment on root turnover at our site, consistent with a global analysis, where no
13 relationship between precipitation and root turnover was found (Gill and Jackson 2000).

14 *Vertical distribution of fine roots*

15 Many studies have found that the majority of roots are located in the top 30 cm of soil
16 (Berhongaray et al. 2015; Di et al. 2018), similar to our study. In this regard, our findings suggest
17 that soil water conditions early in the growing season, particularly during the second month
18 (May at our site), are associated with subsequent patterns in the vertical distribution of fine
19 roots. While soil water content later in the season (e.g., August) showed strong correlations with
20 fine root biomass distribution metrics (β and D50), May soil moisture preceded the main period
21 of root and shoot development and was more consistently related to both fine root biomass and
22 fine root production across our analyses. Previous research has highlighted the significance of
23 this developmental stage in stem growth. During this period of active growth, poplars
24 experience their highest growth rates, contributing to at least 25% of the total stem growth
25 (Trnka et al. 2016). The exact timing of this developmental stage may vary depending on
26 geographic location, local climate, and other factors. Therefore, it would be valuable for future
27 research to explore how soil water availability at different stages of the growing season—early
28 versus late—interacts with plant developmental processes to shape fine root biomass
29 distribution.

30 Our initial hypothesis, that throughfall reduction would directly lead to changes in root
31 production, and turnover, was not fully supported. Nevertheless, the observed shifts in fine root
32 distribution in response to soil water content variations, regardless of the treatment itself, offer
33 valuable insights into the adaptive strategies of poplar plantations under water stress. The

1 significant difference in the β parameter (the extinction coefficient) between the Drought and
2 Control treatments for fine root production suggests that drought stress may influence the
3 vertical distribution of new root growth (Table 4), even if the overall biomass or production
4 remains relatively stable (Table 3). This plasticity in root distribution highlights the ability of
5 poplars to adjust their resource acquisition strategies in response to changing environmental
6 conditions. The observed trends in fine root distribution, production, and turnover offer
7 valuable insights into the adaptive strategies of poplar plantations under water stress. The
8 inherent differences in the functional roles and spatial distribution patterns of coarse and fine
9 roots suggest that variations in coarse root distribution may not directly influence the fine root
10 responses observed in this study (McCormack et al. 2015). The primary function of fine roots is
11 resource acquisition, and their distribution is likely more sensitive to localized changes in soil
12 moisture and nutrient availability, whereas coarse roots primarily provide structural support and
13 long-distance transport (Bardgett et al. 2014; Guo et al. 2021; McCormack et al. 2015).

14 In the current study, we found that root biomass turnover was evenly distributed in the soil
15 profile. This is evidence of a close relationship between root biomass, root production and
16 turnover rate by soil depth, as has been reported elsewhere (Gill and Jackson 2000) , and
17 highlights the importance of considering small-scale heterogeneity in soil water distribution
18 when interpreting these patterns (Beier et al. 2012; Vereecken et al. 2008) . Maximizing the
19 rooting depth of poplars resulted in larger carbon inputs into the subsoil, where it is more
20 efficient to sequester carbon (Rumpel and Kögel-Knabner 2011). New hypotheses should test
21 whether lower soil water availability in the surface soil supports greater carbon sequestration
22 in the deeper soil layers.

23 *Drought effects on fine roots*

24 An earlier study (Orság et al. 2018) illustrated that throughfall exclusion experiments are useful
25 to study the effect of drought on SRC productivity, but at the same time exhibit considerable
26 experimental uncertainty. For example, even though our experimental design achieved very
27 significant differences in throughfall, it did not translate into equally intensive differences in soil
28 water availability between control and drought treatments across the individual subplots (Fig.
29 SM4). The movement of water in soil is indeed a complex process that can make manipulating
30 soil water content through precipitation exclusion experiments challenging (Vereecken et al.
31 2008). Textural differences in the soil profile at our site may also contribute to the observed
32 variability in soil water availability. The pedological survey (Table 1) showed that the combined
33 silt + clay fraction is higher in the upper 45 cm (50–59%) and lower in the 46–80 cm layer (38%).

1 This variation in fine particle content likely influences the soil water retention characteristics,
2 with upper layers generally having a higher water holding capacity. Such textural heterogeneity
3 could interact with precipitation exclusion treatments to produce non-uniform moisture
4 responses across depths and subplots (Fischer et al. 2010). Despite the well-recognized
5 intricacies of soil water movement, this issue has not been adequately addressed in the existing
6 literature on precipitation exclusion experiments (Beier et al. 2012), even though there have
7 been warnings that climate change experiments can alter plot-scale climate in ways that
8 confound the intended treatment effects (Ettinger et al. 2019).

9 While decreases in root biomass due to drought have been reported, the results come from
10 different experimental approaches. Drought effects were reported in greenhouse trials using
11 substrates (Meyer et al. 2021). Similarly, under controlled conditions with potted plants, the
12 activation of specific genes was observed in response to drought, which enhances lateral root
13 formation and biomass growth under water stress (Dash et al. 2017). Simulation models also
14 predict changes in root biomass in response to variations in soil water content (Deckmyn et al.
15 2004). On the other hand, field irrigation experiments in China revealed changes in the vertical
16 distribution of fine roots in the soil profile due to alterations in water content (Zou et al. 2022).
17 Our study provides evidence that such predictions of changes in root dynamics due to drought
18 should be qualified based on geographic location, prevailing climate (especially the
19 Rainfall/Evapotranspiration ratio), experimental design, species, etcetera. Instead of focusing
20 solely on root biomass, models should predict changes in the vertical distribution of roots, as
21 this characteristic seems to be more sensitive to variations in soil water content. While
22 decreases in root biomass have been demonstrated under drought conditions, our findings
23 suggest that the root system's spatial configuration is more responsive to changes in soil water
24 availability, regardless of overall biomass. Models such HYDRUS can effectively simulate the
25 influence of root distribution on water and solute transport (Šimůnek et al. 2006), however, it
26 currently does not explicitly model the feedback of water availability on root growth and
27 distribution. Our findings highlight the need for coupled models that can capture these dynamic
28 interactions to improve predictions of agroforestry system responses to drought. While
29 decreases in root biomass have been demonstrated under drought conditions, our findings
30 suggest that the root system's spatial configuration is more responsive to changes in soil water
31 availability, regardless of the overall biomass.

32

1 Our findings underscore the critical need to integrate root distribution dynamics, beyond mere
2 root biomass, into ecosystem models for improved predictions of terrestrial carbon cycling
3 under drought scenarios. The observed plasticity in root distribution, particularly in regions like
4 central Europe where the direct impact of drought on total root biomass/production was less
5 pronounced, highlights the importance of capturing this adaptive strategy in models. The ability
6 of poplar roots to adjust their vertical distribution in response to changing soil water availability
7 may prove crucial for maintaining productivity and carbon sequestration under future climate
8 change scenarios, characterized by increasing temperatures and more frequent drought events
9 (Forster et al. 2023; IPCC 2021; King et al. 2013). However, the observed variability in soil
10 moisture responses to throughfall reduction underscores the complexity of these interactions
11 and suggests that the adaptive capacity of root systems may be challenged in regions with less
12 predictable rainfall patterns or where soil properties limit water retention. The implications of
13 these findings extend beyond poplar plantations, potentially informing our understanding of the
14 resilience and vulnerability of diverse tree species and forest ecosystems globally.
15 Understanding the complex interplay between climate, soil properties, and root dynamics will
16 be paramount for developing effective strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change on
17 forest ecosystems and ensure their continued provision of essential ecosystem services such as
18 carbon sequestration. Achieving this will require the collection of more empirical data on fine
19 root dynamics across diverse ecosystems, as well as the development of improved models that
20 can more accurately represent root–soil–climate interactions.

21 **Conclusion**

22 This study provides new evidence on the vertical distribution of fine root biomass, production,
23 and turnover in a mature short rotation coppice poplar plantation under varying soil water
24 availability. While total fine root biomass and production were not significantly affected by
25 drought treatment, we observed clear shifts in vertical distribution linked to seasonal variation
26 in soil moisture, particularly during May, a critical phase for stem growth. These findings are
27 consistent with previous studies reporting that fine root distribution is highly sensitive to
28 localized changes in water availability, but differ from other reports that found strong drought
29 effects on total fine root biomass. Our results highlight that root system plasticity—rather than
30 total biomass—may be the key adaptive mechanism under moderate water stress. This vertical
31 adjustment can influence both nutrient uptake efficiency and the depth at which carbon is
32 deposited in the soil, with implications for long-term carbon sequestration. By combining
33 detailed field measurements with established root distribution models, our work emphasizes

1 the importance of integrating root spatial dynamics into models predicting forest and bioenergy
2 crop responses to climate change. Future research should further examine how these plastic
3 responses interact with site-specific climatic and soil conditions to determine ecosystem
4 resilience.

5

1 Bibliography

- 2 Abramoff RZ, Warren J, Harris J, Ottinger SL, Phillips JR, Brenner JM, Garvey SM, Winbourne JB,
3 Smith IA, Reinmann AB (2024) NIST: Soil Respiration, Moisture, Temperature, Chemistry;
4 and Fine Root Measurements from a Transect Through a Forest Edge, Gaithersburg,
5 Maryland, 2017-2021. ORNLTESSFA (Oak Ridge National Lab's Terrestrial Ecosystem
6 Science
- 7 Al Afas N, Marron N, Zavalloni C, Ceulemans R (2008) Growth and production of a short-rotation
8 coppice culture of poplar—IV: fine root characteristics of five poplar clones. *Biomass*
9 *Bioenergy* 32: 494-502.
- 10 An JY, Park BB, Chun JH, Osawa A (2017) Litterfall production and fine root dynamics in cool-
11 temperate forests. *Plos One* 12: e0180126.
- 12 Ardia D, Boudt K, Carl P, Mullen KM, Peterson BG (2011) Differential Evolution with DEoptim An
13 Application to Non-Convex Portfolio Optimization. *R J* 3: 27-34.
- 14 Attia Z, Domec J-C, Oren R, Way DA, Moshelion M (2015) Growth and physiological responses of
15 isohydric and anisohydric poplars to drought. *Journal of experimental botany* 66: 4373-
16 4381.
- 17 Aylott MJ, Casella E, Tubby I, Street N, Smith P, Taylor G (2008) Yield and spatial supply of
18 bioenergy poplar and willow short-rotation coppice in the UK. *New Phytol* 178: 358-370.
- 19 Barchet GL, Dauwe R, Guy RD, Schroeder WR, Soolanayakanahally RY, Campbell MM, Mansfield
20 SD (2014) Investigating the drought-stress response of hybrid poplar genotypes by
21 metabolite profiling. *Tree Physiol* 34: 1203-1219.
- 22 Bardgett RD, Mommer L, De Vries FT (2014) Going underground: root traits as drivers of
23 ecosystem processes. *Trends Ecol Evol* 29: 692-699.
- 24 Beier C, Beierkuhnlein C, Wohlgemuth T, Penuelas J, Emmett B, Körner C, de Boeck H,
25 Christensen JH, Leuzinger S, Janssens IA (2012) Precipitation manipulation experiments—
26 challenges and recommendations for the future. *Ecol Lett* 15: 899-911.
- 27 Berhongaray G, Ceulemans R (2015) Neglected carbon pools and fluxes in the soil balance of
28 short-rotation woody biomass crops. *Biomass Bioenergy* 73: 62-66.
- 29 Berhongaray G, Cotrufo FM, Janssens IA, Ceulemans R (2019) Below-ground carbon inputs
30 contribute more than above-ground inputs to soil carbon accrual in a bioenergy poplar
31 plantation. *Plant Soil* 434: 363-378.
- 32 Berhongaray G, Janssens I, King J, Ceulemans R (2013) Fine root biomass and turnover of two
33 fast-growing poplar genotypes in a short-rotation coppice culture. *Plant Soil* 373: 269-
34 283.
- 35 Berhongaray G, Verlinden MS, Broeckx LS, Ceulemans R (2015) Changes in belowground biomass
36 after coppice in two *Populus* genotypes. *Forest Ecology and Management* 337: 1-10.
- 37 Berhongaray G, Verlinden MS, Broeckx LS, Janssens IA, Ceulemans R (2017) Soil carbon and
38 belowground carbon balance of a short-rotation coppice: assessments from three
39 different approaches. *GCB Bioenergy* 9: 299-313.
- 40 Block R, Van Rees K, Knight J (2006a) A review of fine root dynamics in *Populus* plantations.
41 *Agroforestry Systems* 67: 73-84.
- 42 Block R, Van Rees K, Knight J (2006b) A review of fine root dynamics in *Populus* plantations.
43 *Agrofor Syst* 67: 73-84. doi: 10.1007/s10457-005-2002-7.
- 44 Broeckx LS, Verlinden MS, Berhongaray G, Fichot R, Zona D, Ceulemans R (2013) The effect of a
45 dry spring on seasonal carbon allocation and vegetation dynamics in a poplar bioenergy
46 plantation. *GCB Bioenergy: in press*, DOI:10.1111/gcbb.12087. doi:
47 10.1111/gcbb.12087.
- 48 Brunner I, Bakker MR, Björk RG, Hirano Y, Lukac M, Aranda X, Børja I, Eldhuset TD, Helmisaari H-
49 S, Jourdan C (2013a) Fine-root turnover rates of European forests revisited: an analysis
50 of data from sequential coring and ingrowth cores. *Plant Soil* 362: 357-372.

- 1 Brunner I, Bakker MR, Björk RG, Hirano Y, Lukac M, Aranda X, Børja I, Eldhuset TD, Helmisaari
2 HS, Jourdan C, Konôpka B, López BC, Miguel Pérez C, Persson H, Ostonen I (2013b) Fine-
3 root turnover rates of European forests revisited: an analysis of data from sequential
4 coring and ingrowth cores. *Plant Soil* 362: 357-372. doi: 10.1007/s11104-012-1313-5.
- 5 Brunner I, Herzog C, Dawes MA, Arend M, Sperisen C (2015) How tree roots respond to drought.
6 *Frontiers in plant science* 6: 547.
- 7 Ceulemans R, Deraedt W (1999) Production physiology and growth potential of poplars under
8 short-rotation forestry culture. *Forest Ecol Manag* 121: 9-23.
- 9 Dash M, Yordanov YS, Georgieva T, Tschaplinski TJ, Yordanova E, Busov V (2017) Poplar Ptab ZIP
10 1-like enhances lateral root formation and biomass growth under drought stress. *The*
11 *Plant Journal* 89: 692-705.
- 12 Deckmyn G, Laureysens I, Garcia J, Muys B, Ceulemans R (2004) Poplar growth and yield in short
13 rotation coppice: model simulations using the process model SECRETS. *Biomass*
14 *Bioenerg* 26: 221-227.
- 15 Di N, Liu Y, Mead DJ, Xie Y, Jia L, Xi B (2018) Root-system characteristics of plantation-grown
16 *Populus tomentosa* adapted to seasonal fluctuation in the groundwater table. *Trees* 32:
17 137-149.
- 18 Dickmann DI, Isebrands J, Blake TJ, Kosola K, Kort J (2001) Physiological ecology of poplars.
19 *Poplar Culture in North America*: 77-118.
- 20 Eissenstat D, Wells C, Yanai R, Whitbeck J (2000) Building roots in a changing environment:
21 implications for root longevity. *The New Phytologist* 147: 33-42.
- 22 Ettinger A, Chuine I, Cook B, Dukes J, Ellison A, Johnston M, Panetta A, Rollinson C, Vitasse Y,
23 Wolkovich E (2019) How do climate change experiments alter plot-scale climate? *Ecol*
24 *Lett* 22: 748-763.
- 25 Fairley R, Alexander I (1985) Methods of calculating fine root production in forests In: *Ecological*
26 *Interactions in Soil*. Blackwell Science Inc, Oxford, UK.[Google Scholar].
- 27 Ferré C, Mascetti G, Comolli R (2021) High-density poplar SRC accumulates more soil organic
28 carbon than very-high-density SRC. *Agronomy* 11: 584.
- 29 Fischer M, Trnka M, Kucera J, Deckmyn G, Orsag M, Sedlak P, Zalud Z, Ceulemans R (2013)
30 Evapotranspiration of a high-density poplar stand in comparison with a reference grass
31 cover in the Czech-Moravian Highlands. *Agr Forest Meteorol* 181: 43-60. doi:
32 10.1016/j.agrformet.2013.07.004.
- 33 Fischer M, Trnka M, Kucera J, Zalud Z (2010) Soil water availability in a short rotation poplar
34 coppice (*Populus nigra* × *P. maximowiczii*) in Czech-Moravian Highlands. *Folia Oecologica*
35 37: 23.
- 36 Fischer M, Zenone T, Trnka M, Orsag M, Montagnani L, Ward EJ, Tripathi AM, Hlavinka P, Seufert
37 G, Zalud Z, King JS, Ceulemans R (2018) Water requirements of short rotation poplar
38 coppice: Experimental and modelling analyses across Europe. *Agr Forest Meteorol* 250:
39 343-360. doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2017.12.079.
- 40 Forster PM, Smith CJ, Walsh T, Lamb WF, Lamboll R, Hauser M, Ribes A, Rosen D, Gillett N,
41 Palmer MD (2023) Indicators of Global Climate Change 2022: annual update of large-
42 scale indicators of the state of the climate system and human influence. *Earth System*
43 *Science Data* 15: 2295-2327.
- 44 Freitas ENd, Salgado JCS, Alnoch RC, Contato AG, Habermann E, Michelin M, Martínez CA, Polizeli
45 MdL (2021) Challenges of biomass utilization for bioenergy in a climate change scenario.
46 *Biology* 10: 1277.
- 47 Gale M, Grigal D (1987) Vertical root distributions of northern tree species in relation to
48 successional status. *Can J For Res* 17: 829-834.
- 49 Gill RA, Jackson RB (2000) Global patterns of root turnover for terrestrial ecosystems. *New*
50 *Phytol* 147: 13-31.

- 1 Guo L, Deng M, Yang S, Liu W, Wang X, Wang J, Liu L (2021) The coordination between leaf and
2 fine root litter decomposition and the difference in their controlling factors. Wiley
3 Online Library.
- 4 Guo L, Wang C, Shen RF (2022) Stronger effects of maize rhizosphere than phosphorus
5 fertilization on phosphatase activity and phosphorus-mineralizing-related bacteria in
6 acidic soils. *Rhizosphere* 23: 100555.
- 7 Herve C, Ceulemans R (1996) Short-rotation coppiced vs non-coppiced poplar: A comparative
8 study at two different field sites. *Biomass Bioenerg* 11: 139-150. doi: 10.1016/0961-
9 9534(96)00028-1.
- 10 Hu H, Bao W, Huang L, Li F (2024) Shifting patterns in fine root distribution of four xerophytic
11 species across soil structural gradients and years of growth. *Ecology and Evolution* 14:
12 e10889.
- 13 IPCC (2021) The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report WGIII climate assessment of mitigation pathways:
14 from emissions to global temperatures. IPCC.
- 15 Jackson RB, Canadell J, Ehleringer JR, Mooney H, Sala O, Schulze E-D (1996) A global analysis of
16 root distributions for terrestrial biomes. *Oecologia* 108: 389-411.
- 17 Kengdo SK, Ahrens B, Tian Y, Heinzle J, Wanek W, Schindlbacher A, Borken W (2023) Increase in
18 carbon input by enhanced fine root turnover in a long-term warmed forest soil. *Science*
19 *of the Total Environment* 855: 158800.
- 20 King JS, Ceulemans R, Albaugh JM, Dillen SY, Domec J-C, Fichot R, Fischer M, Leggett Z, Sucre E,
21 Trnka M (2013) The challenge of lignocellulosic bioenergy in a water-limited world.
22 *BioScience* 63: 102-117.
- 23 Králík T, Knápek J, Vávrová K, Outrata D, Romportl D, Horák M, Jandera J (2023) Ecosystem
24 services and economic competitiveness of perennial energy crops in the modelling of
25 biomass potential—A case study of the Czech Republic. *Renewable and Sustainable*
26 *Energy Reviews* 173: 113120.
- 27 Levillain J, Thongo M'Bou A, Deleporte P, Saint-André L, Jourdan C (2011) Is the simple auger
28 coring method reliable for below-ground standing biomass estimation in Eucalyptus
29 forest plantations? *Ann Bot-London* 108: 221-230.
- 30 Lindström A, Stattin E (1994) Root freezing tolerance and vitality of Norway spruce and Scots
31 pine seedlings; influence of storage duration, storage temperature, and prestorage root
32 freezing. *Can J For Res* 24: 2477-2484.
- 33 Maeght J-L, Rewald B, Pierret A (2013) How to study deep roots—and why it matters. *Frontiers*
34 *in plant science* 4: 299.
- 35 McCormack ML, Dickie IA, Eissenstat DM, Fahey TJ, Fernandez CW, Guo D, Helmisaari HS, Hobbie
36 EA, Iversen CM, Jackson RB (2015) Redefining fine roots improves understanding of
37 below-ground contributions to terrestrial biosphere processes. *New Phytol* 207: 505-
38 518.
- 39 McCormack ML, Guo D (2014) Impacts of environmental factors on fine root lifespan. *Frontiers*
40 *in Plant Science* 5: 205.
- 41 Meyer M, Morgenstern K, Heilig D, Heil B, Kovács G, Leibing C, Krabel D (2021) Biomass
42 Allocation and Root Characteristics of Early-Stage Poplars (*Populus* spp.) for Assessing
43 Their Water-Deficit Response During SRC Establishment. *Bioenergy Res* 14: 385-398.
- 44 Mullen KM, Ardia D, Gil DL, Windover D, Cline J (2011) DEoptim: An R Package for Global
45 Optimization by Differential Evolution. *J Stat Softw* 40: 1-26.
- 46 Nielsen KL, Lynch JP, JablOKow AG, Curtis PS (1994) Carbon cost of root systems: an architectural
47 approach. *Plant Soil* 165: 161-169.
- 48 Orsag M, Fischer M, Tripathi AM, Zalud Z, Trnka M (2018) Sensitivity of short rotation poplar
49 coppice biomass productivity to the throughfall reduction - Estimating future drought
50 impacts. *Biomass Bioenerg* 109: 182-189. doi: 10.1016/j.biombioe.2017.12.028.
- 51 Philippot L, Raaijmakers JM, Lemanceau P, Van Der Putten WH (2013) Going back to the roots:
52 the microbial ecology of the rhizosphere. *Nature reviews microbiology* 11: 789-799.

- 1 Pierret A, Maeght J-L, Clément C, Montoroi J-P, Hartmann C, Gonkhamdee S (2016)
2 Understanding deep roots and their functions in ecosystems: an advocacy for more
3 unconventional research. *Ann Bot-London* 118: 621-635.
- 4 Pregitzer KS, King JS, Burton AJ, Brown SE (2000) Responses of tree fine roots to temperature.
5 *New Phytol* 147: 105-115.
- 6 Regier N, Streb S, Cocozza C, Schaub M, Cherubini P, Zeeman SC, Frey B (2009) Drought tolerance
7 of two black poplar (*Populus nigra* L.) clones: contribution of carbohydrates and
8 oxidative stress defence. *Plant Cell Environ* 32: 1724-1736.
- 9 Rumpel C, Kögel-Knabner I (2011) Deep soil organic matter—a key but poorly understood
10 component of terrestrial C cycle. *Plant Soil* 338: 143-158.
- 11 Sasse J, Martinoia E, Northen T (2018) Feed your friends: do plant exudates shape the root
12 microbiome? *Trends in plant science* 23: 25-41.
- 13 Schenk HJ, Jackson RB (2002a) The global biogeography of roots. *Ecol Monogr* 72: 311-328.
- 14 Schenk HJ, Jackson RB (2002b) Rooting depths, lateral root spreads and below-ground/above-
15 ground allometries of plants in water-limited ecosystems. *Journal of Ecology* 90: 480-
16 494.
- 17 Schmidt-Walter P, Trotsiuk V, Meusburger K, Zacios M, Meesenburg H (2020) Advancing
18 simulations of water fluxes, soil moisture and drought stress by using the LWF-Brook90
19 hydrological model in R. *Agr Forest Meteorol* 291: 108023.
- 20 Schweier J, Molina-Herrera S, Ghirardo A, Grote R, Díaz-Pinés E, Kreuzwieser J, Haas E,
21 Butterbach-Bahl K, Rennenberg H, Schnitzler JP (2017) Environmental impacts of
22 bioenergy wood production from poplar short-rotation coppice grown at a marginal
23 agricultural site in Germany. *GCB Bioenergy* 9: 1207-1221.
- 24 Šimůnek J, Van Genuchten MT, Šejna M (2006) The HYDRUS software package for simulating
25 two-and three-dimensional movement of water, heat, and multiple solutes in variably-
26 saturated media. Technical manual, version 1: 241.
- 27 Sprunger CD, Oates LG, Jackson RD, Robertson GP (2017) Plant community composition
28 influences fine root production and biomass allocation in perennial bioenergy cropping
29 systems of the upper Midwest, USA. *Biomass Bioenerg* 105: 248-258.
- 30 Team RC (2023) A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing In: *FfS Computing* (ed).
31 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- 32 Tripathi AM, Klem K, Fischer M, Orsag M, Trnka M, Marek MV (2018) Water availability
33 influences accumulation and allocation of nutrients and metals in short-rotation poplar
34 plantation. *Biomass Bioenerg* 116: 151-160. doi: 10.1016/j.biombioe.2018.06.010.
- 35 Trnka M, Fischer M, Bartošová L, Orsag M, Kyncl T, Ceulemans R, King J, Büntgen U (2016)
36 Potential and limitations of local tree ring records in estimating a priori the growth
37 performance of short-rotation coppice plantations. *Biomass Bioenerg* 92: 12-19.
- 38 Vargas R, Trumbore SE, Allen MF (2009) Evidence of old carbon used to grow new fine roots in
39 a tropical forest. *New Phytol*: 710-718.
- 40 Vereecken H, Huisman J, Bogaen H, Vanderborght J, Vrugt J, Hopmans J (2008) On the value of
41 soil moisture measurements in vadose zone hydrology: A review. *Water resources*
42 *research* 44.
- 43 Wang Y, Gao G, Wang N, Wang Z, Gu J (2019) Effects of morphology and stand structure on root
44 biomass and length differed between absorptive and transport roots in temperate trees.
45 *Plant Soil* 442: 355-367.
- 46 Wildy DT, Pate JS, Sefcik LT (2004) Water-use efficiency of a mallee eucalypt growing naturally
47 and in short-rotation coppice cultivation. *Plant Soil* 262: 111-128.
- 48 Withington JM, Reich PB, Oleksyn J, Eissenstat DM (2006) Comparisons of structure and life span
49 in roots and leaves among temperate trees. *Ecol Monogr* 76: 381-397.
- 50 Zalesny Jr RS, Berndes G, Dimitriou I, Fritsche U, Miller C, Eisenbies M, Ghezehei S, Hazel D,
51 Headlee WL, Mola-Yudego B (2019) Positive water linkages of producing short rotation

1 poplars and willows for bioenergy and phytotechnologies. Wiley Interdisciplinary
2 Reviews: Energy and Environment 8: e345.
3 Zou S, Li D, Di N, Liu J, Li L, Liu Y, Xi B, Coleman M (2022) Stand development modifies effects of
4 soil water availability on poplar fine-root traits: evidence from a six-year experiment.
5 Plant Soil 480: 165-184.
6

1 **Statements and Declarations**

2 **Funding**

3 This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic
4 for under the project AdAgriF – Advanced methods of greenhouse gases emission reduction and
5 sequestration in agriculture and forest landscape for climate change mitigation
6 (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635). G.B. received a grant from the Erasmus-Mundus External
7 Cooperation Consortium EADIC – Window Lot 16 financed by the European Union Mobility
8 Programme # 2009–1655/001–001. M.T. acknowledges support from National Agency for
9 Agricultural Research as part of project No. QK23020013 – Finding DZES 5 measures to protect
10 agricultural land from wind erosion and land drying.

11

12 **Competing Interests**

13 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

14

15 **Author Contributions**

16 All authors contributed to the study conception and design. The drought experiment was
17 designed by Miroslav Trnka and John King and performed in the field by Milan Fischer and Matěj
18 Orság. The root experiment was designed by Gonzalo Berhongaray, data collection and analysis
19 were performed mainly by Abishek Tripathi, with support from Gonzalo Berhongaray, Milan
20 Fischer and Matěj Orság. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Gonzalo Berhongaray
21 and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and
22 approved the final manuscript.

23

24 **Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing**

25 Generative AI was used in the writing process to improve the readability and language of the
26 manuscript. After using this tool, Gonzalo Berhongaray reviewed and edited the content as
27 needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

28

29 **Data Availability**

30 We declare that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper and
31 its Supplementary Information files. Should any raw data files be needed in another format they
32 are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

- 1 **Table 1.** Soil silt + clay fraction, organic matter, pH and total nitrogen of the soil layer at
2 Domanínek plantation.

Soil depth (cm)	Silt + clay (%)	Organic matter (%)	pH (KCl)	Total N (%)
0-20	50	1.12	6.2	0.072
21-45	59	0.55	6.1	0.036
46-80	38	-	-	-

3

4

1 **Table 2.** Mass of dead and live roots (g DM m⁻²) by depth and drought treatment sampled in February 2014 at Domanínek plantation. Values are presented as
 2 means ± one standard error, with the same letter indicating no statistically significant difference between drought treatment within each diameter class and
 3 soil depth and soil depth (ANOVA; p>0.05). 0–1 mm, 1–2 mm and 0–2 mm represents the diameter class of the roots (n= 18 (6 locations × 3 blocks)), DM = dry
 4 mass, and FR = total live fine roots.

Depth (cm)	Dead roots (g DM m ⁻²)				Live roots (g DM m ⁻²)							
	Control		Drought		0–1 mm		1–2 mm		FR (0–2 mm)			
	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
0-15	49.9 ±9.1 a	46.1 ±7.5 a	122.6 ±11.4 a	116.8 ±13.7 a	52.7 ±10.2 a	54.8 ±8.2 a	175.2 ±17.4 a	171.6 ±19.2 a				
15-30	7.5 ±1.4 a	10.1 ±3.9 a	33.3 ±3.4 a	21.0 ±3.2 b	10.5 ±3.6 a	11.6 ±4.4 a	42.0 ±5.2 a	32.0 ±6.9 a				
30-45	7.4 ±1.4 a	7.1 ±2.1 a	22.7 ±3.3 a	13.9 ±2.8 b	10.2 ±3.4 a	13.2 ±4.8 a	32.2 ±5.9 a	27.1 ±6.0 a				
45-60	11.4 ±4.4 a	4.0 ±0.8 a	10.7 ±3.4 a	13.2 ±4.0 a	5.0 ±2.7 a	2.5 ±1.3 a	15.7 ±5.1 a	16.1 ±4.9 a				

5

6

- 1 **Table 3.** Production (top) and turnover rates (bottom) of roots from February to November 2014 of different diameter classes by depth and drought treatment.
- 2 Values are presented as means \pm one standard error, with the same letter indicating no statistically significant difference between control and drought
- 3 treatment of each root diameter class and soil depth (ANOVA; $p > 0.05$). 0–1 mm, 1–2 mm and 0–2 mm represents the diameter of the roots.

Production (g DM m ⁻² y ⁻¹)										
Depth (cm)	n	0–1 mm		1–2 mm		FR (0–2 mm)				
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought			
0-15	9	170.1 \pm 14.7 a	139.1 \pm 11.7 a	42.5 \pm 2.9 a	39.6 \pm 13.0 a	212.7 \pm 16.7 a	178.7 \pm 21.9 a			
15-30	9	46.3 \pm 11.5 a	37.4 \pm 5.9 a	9.2 \pm 0.9 a	13.9 \pm 5.7 a	54.9 \pm 11.1 a	51.3 \pm 0.5 a			
30-45	9	23.8 \pm 6.7 a	18.6 \pm 1.3 a	3.9 \pm 2.5 a	7.5 \pm 7.5 a	30.0 \pm 6.0 a	26.1 \pm 6.3 a			
45-60	9	15.3 \pm 3.7 a	14.0 \pm 4.9 a	9.1 \pm 7.3 a	7.0 \pm 3.4 a	21.3 \pm 6.9 a	21.0 \pm 1.9 a			
0-60	9	255.5 \pm 22.6 a	209.2 \pm 3.4 a	64.6 \pm 4.2 a	67.9 \pm 16.0 a	318.8 \pm 24.5 a	277.0 \pm 19.4 a			
Turnover (y ⁻¹)										
0-15	9	1.68 \pm 0.2 a	1.77 \pm 0.2 a	1.28 \pm 0.3 a	1.13 \pm 0.2 a	1.57 \pm 0.2 a	1.58 \pm 0.2 a			
15-30	9	1.90 \pm 0.3 a	1.87 \pm 0.5 a	1.44 \pm 0.7 a	1.30 \pm 0.8 a	1.76 \pm 0.4 a	1.58 \pm 0.3 a			
30-45	9	1.47 \pm 0.3 a	2.47 \pm 0.7 a	0.93 \pm 0.9 a	0.51 \pm 0.3 a	1.48 \pm 0.4 a	1.75 \pm 0.2 a			
45-60	9	2.29 \pm 1.0 a	1.76 \pm 0.5 a	0.99 \pm 0.3 a	2.00 \pm 1.1 a	1.72 \pm 1.9 a	1.96 \pm 0.4 a			

4

5

1 **Table 4.** Percentile 10–90 (P10–P90) and average values of the parameters β , D_{50} and c for the
 2 control and drought treatment. The β parameter of the asymptotic equation (Jackson *et al.*
 3 1996) and c and D_{50} parameters of the logistic dose–response curve model (Schenk and Jackson
 4 2002) were fit to the vertical distribution of the fine root biomass and fine root production. p-
 5 values are from the ANOVA analysis.

Fine root biomass						
Treatment	β		c		D_{50}	
	P10 – P90	mean	P10 – P90	mean	P10 – P90	mean
Control	(0.86 – 0.96)	0.93	(1.48 – 3.17)	2.12	(4.52 – 14.41)	11.27
Drought	(0.84 – 0.96)	0.92	(1.06 – 4.88)	2.11	(0.42 – 17.54)	9.89
p-value		0.80		0.97		0.58
Fine root production						
Control	(0.85 – 0.97)	0.91	(3.77 – 1.20)	2.01	(1.99 – 19.94)	9.57
Drought	(0.91 – 0.96)	0.94	(4.37 – 1.31)	2.06	(6.23 – 14.4)	11.65
p-value		<0.01		0.81		0.10

6

7